

Review of Teaching Methods for Enhancement of Academic Achievements of Co-education and Single-Sex Students in Senior Secondary School Biology.

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Abstract

This study investigated review of teaching methods for enhancement of academic achievement of co-education and single-sex students in senior school biology, using quasi-experimental research design. The sample size was 323 Senior Secondary School Two students from 23 Senior Secondary Schools in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas, with population size of 6,988 SS2 students offering Biology as a subject in Secondary School in Bayelsa State. One research question and one hypothesis were used for the study. Guide on Lecture Method, Discussion Method Guide and Guide on Demonstration Method were guides used by teachers on how to use the teaching methods. Standardized Biology Achievement Test was adopted as instrument for collection of data. Percentage, mean, standard deviation and z-test statistics were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that no significant difference exist in the mean scores of SS2 students in co-education and single-sex schools taught with demonstration method in academic achievement in Biology. Also, a substantial variance exist in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with demonstration and lecture methods in academic achievement in Biology. Recommendations made include appropriate use of teaching methods should be considered in line with population size in order to enhance students' academic performance in biology.

Keywords: Discussion Method, Demonstration Method, Lecture Method, Achievement, Biology, Education.

Introduction

Education is a structured process that equips students with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and norms that will benefit both them and society as a whole. It involves adjusting a learner's behavior and character to conform to social norms. Education, according to Obanya (2023), is more than just memorizing facts, numeracy, and manipulative abilities; it is also about developing cognitive, life, and lifelong learning skills. According to Amosa and Olubode (2013) and Ogundiwin and Olusa (2017), education has a significant role in optimizing students' potential and abilities and serves as a gauge for significant and long-term national development. According to Adeyemo

(2012), education is an investment that will benefit society greatly in the long term. This is why the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) established equal right to high-quality education for all people, both inside and outside of the formal school system.

There are concerns about the fall in educational standards despite claims that education is the cornerstone of progress in every country, including Nigeria (Adesehinwa, 2013). According to Aghadaino in Igbojinwaekwu (2012b), there is a believe that biology is the easiest of the science topics, hence, senior secondary school students choose to enroll in biology rather than physics and chemistry at the external examination level. As biology is thought to be the easiest, it is assumed that students will perform at the highest level; however, when compared to other science disciplines, biology has the lowest results. Poor academic performance in science, and biology specifically, is still on the rise (Awodun, Adekunle, & Femi-Adeoye, 2016; Auwalu, Mohd & Muhammad, 2014). According to Badmus and Omosewo (2018), the Chief Examiner's Report for the WASSCE from 2007 to 2016 revealed that science academic performance has recently fallen short of expectations, especially in biology. When biology students' academic performance was compared to that of physics and chemistry students, biology students performed the worst on external exams. According to the Chief Examiner's Report, 2022, another WAEC report referenced in Adebajo & Yusuf (2022), credit pass in biology decreased to almost 30% between 2017 and 2022. Students, parents, instructors, stakeholders, and the country as a whole are concerned about this decline in student achievement (WAEC, Chief Examiner's Report, 2022). This showed that in the previous ten years, fewer than half of candidates who registered for and completed WAEC were able to get admission to postsecondary institutions to pursue science-related courses (Adebajo & Yusuf, 2022). The development of science, technology, and national progress are all seriously threatened by this.

Today, there are a number of innovative and contemporary teaching methods that are helpful resources for science instruction. Since no teaching style is better than another, new approaches should complement one another when necessary rather than entirely eliminating the usage of old methods (Cleopas & Igbojinwaekwu, 2023). According to Okonronka (as cited in Igbojinwaekwu, 2016), teaching methods are a process used to accomplish a specific goal. Igbojinwaekwu and Dorgu (as cited in Igbojinwaekwu, 2016) described teaching strategies as a framework that directs educators in instructing students in order to meet predetermined goals. When choosing and implementing instructional strategies in the teaching and learning process, innovation, creativity, and dynamism should be taken into account. Thus, the use of teaching methods is crucial to students' academic success (Ayeni, 2010; Eila, Irmeli and Eya, 2016). The lecture method is the earliest approach and is still widely used in schools today, according to Ameh and Dantani (2012) and Edingyang, Ubi and Adaliku (2012). It could be because it is simpler to use for covering heavy syllabi (Ameh & Dantani, 2012) and in large class sizes (Achimugu, 2018).

A school type could be determined by its ownership and the gender of its students. It could be coeducation, single-sex, private, or public. Among the variables influencing learning attitude, retention rate, and academic achievement is school type (Hussaini et al, 2015; Yousuf & Bhutta, 2012). Researchers have found that school type significantly affects biology students' academic achievement, retention rate, and learning attitude (Oginni et al., 2013; Egbule as cited in Oghenevwe, 2012; Gbore & Daramola, 2013). According to others (Isah et al., 2019), school type has little bearing on academic achievement, retention rate, or learning attitude. According to certain research (Teba, 2020; Ademe, 2016), gender-biased environments, poor communication skills, complex and socialization issues are the main causes of single-sex schools' low academic

success, retention rate, and learning attitude. This contrasts with the findings of Igbojinwaekwu (as cited in Igbojinwaekwu & Torunarigha, 2012), who found that since more female science teachers are teaching and learning science in the modern era, students in single-sex schools, particularly those for girls, no longer face complex socialization challenges.

Mixed-sex schools are known as coeducation schools. According to research, coeducation schools offer their students greater advantages over single-sex schools in the areas of socialization, interaction, and participation in class activities, as well as in the learning environment, idea sharing, respect for the other sex, healthy gender competition, and the capacity to compete and fit in with society norms (Ademe, 2016; Igbojinwaekwu as cited in Igbojinwaekwu & Torunarigha, 2012). These characteristics influence biology students' learning attitudes, retention rates, and academic success.

Single-sex schools are schools that have gender bias either for male or female only. They are schools for only males or females. The study of Ogundiwin and Olusa (2017) revealed that biological, psychological and social life of learners have a great impact on learning of science. This is perhaps due to negative comparison of performance and label which has led to gender gap in science, poor attitude to science and academic achievement. The study of Yoloye (2011) revealed that poor academic achievement in co-education schools is common among female students because of belief that science is gender bias than in single-sex schools. Incessant poor academic achievement perhaps led to idea of single-sex schools. Advocates of single-sex schools are of the opinion that when male and female students are in different classrooms and schools, they have better academic achievement (James as cited in Ogundiwin & Olusa 2017). Juliet and Shokare (2014) advocated for conversion of co-education schools into single-sex schools because improved gender discipline that enhanced better academic achievement in females was seen. Kibona and Nkya (2024) revealed that single-sex schools outperformed students in co-education schools. Also, girls' enrolment and in science was more in single sex schools than in co-education schools. This study concludes that single-sex schools is an important conclusion to attaining the Sustainable Development Goals 4 (SDG4) by 2030. Research also hold that boys are better represented in chemistry and physics than in biology (Ogundiwin & Olusa, 2017). This show that there is a still gender gap in science participation today and it is seen in engineering, technology and other sciences as underrepresentation of females in these careers.

There are many studies on the effects of coeducational schools on academic achievement in many locations on various variables, but there are few studies on how teaching methods affect academic achievement in biology classes for senior school students who are single-sex and coeducational. Also, from the review of related literature, it was observed that studies on co-education schools are available but very few studies on single-sex schools in terms of academic achievement of students in biology, hence, gaps in literature, population and empirical studies of the study. This is the why of the study, review of teaching methods for enhancement of academic achievement of single-sex and co-education students in senior school biology in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas, Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria today, there is a lot of worry about the quality of science education, and biology in particular, in senior school. One of the prerequisites for taking university courses in medicine, pharmacy, botany, zoology, and science education is biology. Although it is crucial for getting into college, biology students in senior school perform poorly academically (Chief Examiner's Report,

WAEC 2022). Numerous issues have been identified by various research as the reasons behind biology students' low academic performance. Despite government intervention to provide a 60:40 ratio in favor of sciences for admission into tertiary institutions, the decline in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics and poor academic achievement in science as a result of prevailing issues in the education community is evident.

According to Badmus and Omosewo (2018), academic performance in biology from the West African Examination Council showed that between 2007 and 2012, about 30% of candidate registrations had credit pass and above in biology, while between 2013 and 2016, only about 50% of registrations had credit pass and above in biology. Research indicates that senior school biology students perform the worst on external exams, with the highest enrollment and lowest accomplishment, and this is related to the way biology is taught (Tata, Abba & Abdullahi, 2014; Nsa, Ikot & Udo, 2013; Oyekan, 2013; Arokoyu & Chukwu, 2017). It is on this premise that the study sought to investigate review of teaching methods for enhancement of academic achievement of single-sex and co-education students in senior school biology in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the difference that exists between the mean achievement scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

Research Question

1. What difference exist between the mean achievement scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods?

Null Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools, taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

Method

A pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental research design was used in this study. This was because the participation of intact classes made complete randomization impractical (Thyer, 2012). There were 6,988 senior school two (SS2) students, 3,819 of them were male and 3,169 were female, spread over 37 senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Areas, from Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas. 23 randomly chosen schools from the two Local Government Areas served as sampled schools. Schools were selected based on their willingness to participate in the experiment and their experienced teachers who had at least three years of biology teaching experience. Based on the students' enrollment in Senior School Two (SS2), their study of biology, and their pretest scores of forty percent (40%) or higher, sampled students were purposefully chosen. This is to certify that the samples used were of equal standing and are comparable (Akuezilo & Agu, 2004). The choice of the locale was based on convenience of road network, due to topography of the state and must have single-sex schools, private and public schools which must be good road network. 323 biology students who scored forty percent (40%) and above in the pretest, were purposively selected out of 779 biology students in the 23 schools and make up the sample size that was used, in order, to certify that samples used were of equal

standing and were comparable (Akuezuido & Agu, 2004). Students wrote their first name on the script in addition to assigned codes for easy Identification. Students who scored less than 40% were allowed in the class in order not to disorganized the school administration. All eligible students did the tests but not all the students were part of the sample because students' scripts with below 40% were not used for the research. Three validated and reliable instructional guides namely Discussion Method Guide (DMG), Guide on Demonstration Method (GDM) and Guide on Lecture Method (GLM) were utilized. Standardized Biology Achievement Test (SBAT) was adapted from West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) question papers as instrument for the study. The reliability index of SBAT was not calculated because the questions were not teachers' made test. According to Stanley and Hopkin (as cited in Egbule, 2002), standardized achievement tests were tests which have been processed for reliability and validity, hence, they are very reliable, valid and extensive in application. The students were given pretest before treatment to examine their prior knowledge of biology and to provide the researcher a ground knowledge of students to start the experiment. Students took posttest after four weeks of teaching and learning process. Percentage and mean tools were used for data analysis of research question. Posttest mean, standard deviation and z-test were used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant level on a 2-tailed test.

Results

Research Question One

What difference exist between the mean achievement scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods?

Table 1: Summary of Mean Achievement Scores of SS2 Students in Single-sex and Co-education Schools taught Biology using Demonstration, Discussion and Lecture Methods

Teaching Method	School Type	N	Pretest \bar{x}	Posttest \bar{x}
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	46.41	45.92
	Co-education	70	51.21	47.94
Difference			4.80	2.02
Discussion	Single-sex	26	51.92	62.11
	Co-education	89	57.32	53.77
Difference			5.40	8.34
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	46.41	45.92
		27	46.18	51.00
Difference			0.23	5.08
Demonstration	Co-education	70	51.21	47.94
		60	50.61	58.76
Difference			0.6	10.82
Discussion	Single-sex	26	51.92	62.11
		27	46.18	51.00
Difference			5.74	11.11
Discussion	Co-education	89	57.32	53.77
		60	50.61	58.76
Difference			6.71	4.99

Answer to research question one, Table 1 shows academic achievement means of single sex students (46.41) and co-education school students (51.21) at pretest with a difference of 4.80 to advantage of co-education school students when taught with demonstration method. When taught with demonstration method, at posttest, single-sex students had 45.92 academic achievement mean and co-education school students had 47.94 academic achievement mean with a difference of 2.02 to advantage of co-education school students. At pretest, when taught with discussion method, single-sex school students had 51.92 mean and co-education school students had 57.32 mean with a difference of 5.40 to advantage of co-education school students. When taught with discussion method, at posttest, single-sex school students had 62.11 academic achievement mean and co-education school students had 53.77 academic achievement mean with a difference of 8.34 to advantage of co-education school students. In control group, at pretest, single-sex school students had 46.18 academic achievement mean and co-education school students had 50.16 academic achievement mean with a difference of 4.43 to advantage of co-education school students. At posttest, single-sex school students had academic achievement mean of 51.00 and co-education school students had academic achievement mean of 58.76 with a difference of 7.76 to advantage of co-education school students when taught with lecture method. This implies that co-education school students had better academic attainment mean than single-sex school students. In addition, this table shows a difference of 0.23 academic attainment mean to advantage of single-sex students taught with demonstration teaching method and 0.6 academic achievement mean to advantage of co-education school students taught with demonstration teaching method at pretest. At posttest, a difference of 5.08 academic achievement mean to advantage of single-sex school students taught with lecture teaching method and a difference of 10.82 academic achievement mean to advantage of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method. Also, a difference of 5.74 academic achievement mean to advantage of single-sex school students taught with discussion teaching method and a difference of 6.71 academic achievement mean to advantage of co-education school students taught with discussion teaching method at pretest. At posttest, a difference of 11.11 academic achievement mean to advantage of single-sex school students taught with discussion teaching method and a difference of 4.99 academic achievement mean to advantage of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools, taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

Table 2: Summary of z- test Analysis of Single-sex and Co-education Schools SS2 Students Achievement taught using Demonstration, Discussion and Lecture Methods

Teaching Method	Sch Type	N	Posttest \bar{x}	SD	df	Z_{cal}	Z_{crit}	Type of test	P
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	45.92	9.71	119	0.78	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	70	47.94	18.40					
Discussion	Single-sex	26	62.11	13.14	113	2.89	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	89	53.77	12.38					
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	45.92	9.71	76	1.62	1.98	2-tailed	<0.05
	Lecture	27	51.00	14.61					
Demonstration	Single-sex	70	47.94	18.40	128	3.38	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Lecture	60	58.76	18.04					
Discussion	Single-sex	26	62.11	13.14	51	2.91	1.98	2-tailed	<0.05
	Lecture	27	51.00	14.61					
Lecture	Single-sex	89	53.77	12.38	147	1.86	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	60	58.76	18.04					

When hypothesis 1, H_{01} , was subjected to z-test investigation, it was revealed that the z-calculated value is 0.78, while the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with demonstration method. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected since the z-calculated value is less than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education and single-sex schools taught with demonstration method in academic achievement in Biology. It was also discovered that the z-calculated value is 2.89 and the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with discussion method. The null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted since the z-calculated value is better than the z-critical value. This means that there is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education and single-sex schools taught with discussion method in academic achievement in Biology.

It was revealed that the z-calculated value is 1.62, while the z-critical value is 1.98 when taught with demonstration and lecture methods. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected since the z-calculated value is less than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single sex schools taught with demonstration and lecture methods in academic achievement in Biology. It was also discovered that the z-calculated value is 3.38 and the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with demonstration and lecture methods. The null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted since the z-calculated value is better than the z-critical value. This means that there is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with demonstration and lecture methods in academic achievement in Biology.

It was also discovered that the z-calculated value is 2.91 and the z-critical value is 1.98 when taught with discussion and lecture methods. The null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted since the z-calculated value is better than the z-critical value. This means that there is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single sex schools taught with discussion and lecture methods in academic achievement in Biology. It was revealed that the z-

calculated value is 1.86, while the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with discussion and lecture methods. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected since the z-calculated value is less than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with discussion and lecture methods in academic achievement in Biology.

Discussion

From research question one, students in co-education schools taught with demonstration method outperformed students in single-sex schools taught with demonstration method in terms of academic achievement but results of z-test analysis showed non-substantial. The mean scores of SS2 students in co-education and single-sex schools taught with demonstration method do not differ significantly in academic achievement in Biology. This finding agrees with the finding of Chanda (2023), that mean grades of students in single-sex schools and co-education schools had no substantial variance in science and mathematics. This result may be probably because gender is no longer an issue in science as single-sex school students do not have complex challenge anymore since more female science teachers are involved in teaching and learning of science in recent times. This is also in agreement with O'Neill (2011). According to him, single-sex school students are more at ease in their environment which encourage them to participate actively and ask questions in learning. Their environment improves better academic achievement than co-education school students. This finding is in contrast with the work of Kelly and Oloyede (2019) who are of the opinion that students in single-sex schools had better academic achievement than students in co-education schools. Perhaps, this is due to social influence in the co-education schools. The study also contradict the study of Igbojinwaekwu (as cited in Igbojinwaekwu & Torunarigha, 2012). They reported that co-education schools have more lead than single-sex schools in terms of exchange of ideas, socialization, respect for opposite sex, participation in class activities, interaction, healthy competition between gender and ability to compete favourably outside school and in life. While the findings of Ogundiwin and Olusa (2017) showed that students in single-sex schools performed better in chemistry, physics and biology than students from co-education schools.

Also, single-sex students taught with discussion method outperformed co-education school students taught with discussion method but when z-test analysis was carried out, result showed substantial. The mean scores of SS2 students in co-education and single-sex schools taught with discussion method showed a significant difference in academic achievement in Biology. This is in agreement with Chanda (2023) who revealed that single-sex students perform better than students in co-education schools. Also, many teachers and learners prefer single-sex schools due to limited participation of females, inappropriate behaviours among male students and favoritism of the female students in co-education schools. Also, Egbule (as cited in Oghenevwede, 2012; Busari (2016) reported that active students' participation led to better academic achievement in single-sex schools. This is in contradiction with the work of Teba (2020). The study noted that lack of collaboration exist in single-sex students due to socialization issue, hence, poor academic achievement in students. Their environment is gender biased and affect their academic achievement (James (as cited in Ogundiwin and Olusa. 2017; Teba 2020). Also, in the study of Ogundiwin and Olusa (2017), it was reported that female students in single-sex schools had better academic attainment in science and mathematics than girls in co-education schools because of intimidation by the presence of male students in the co-education schools. It is also supported by the work of Pahlke, Hyde & Allison (2014).

Single-sex school students taught with lecture method outperformed single-sex school students taught with demonstration method but when result was subjected to z-test analysis, it showed non-substantial. The mean scores of students in single-sex schools taught with demonstration and lecture methods showed no substantial difference in academic achievement in Biology. Also, co-education school students taught with lecture method outperformed co-education school students taught with demonstration method and when result was subjected to z-test analysis, it showed substantial. The mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with demonstration and lecture methods had a substantial variance in academic achievement in Biology. This is probably because lecture method is content and examination oriented and demonstration method is disadvantaged due to large population size. This is supported by Nwagbo & Ajaja (as cited in Oghenevwe, 2012).

Single-sex school students taught with discussion method achieved better than single-sex school students taught with lecture method but when result was subjected to z-test analysis, it showed substantial. The mean scores of students in single-sex schools taught with discussion and lecture methods showed a substantial variance in academic achievement in Biology. This was perhaps due to students' participation, interaction and active involvement in lessons which facilitated understanding of lessons and in return increased academic achievement. This is supported by the work of Albert et al, (2014). Co-education school students taught with lecture method outperformed co-education school students taught with discussion method but when result was subjected to z-test analysis, it showed non-substantial. The mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with discussion and lecture methods showed no substantial variance in academic achievement in Biology.

Conclusion

The study revealed no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught with demonstration method in academic achievement in Biology. Lack of significant difference in mean grades of students in co-education and single-sex schools in science and mathematics was perhaps because more female science teachers are involved in teaching and learning process of science in modern times which cancels complex challenge in single-sex students. Also, there is a substantial difference in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with demonstration and lecture methods in academic achievement in Biology. This is probably because lecture teaching method is content and examination oriented and demonstration method is disadvantaged due to large population size.

Recommendations

1. The use of appropriate teaching methods should be considered along side class size in order to make more impact in teaching and learning.
2. The government should consider establishment of more single-sex schools in order to enhance girls' enrollment and in science to achieve SDG4 2030.

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